

Nitration. Part V. Nitration of Monohalogenated Derivatives of Xylenes.

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The nitro-derivatives of monohalogenated (*o*-, *m*-, and *p*-) xylenes have been obtained mostly by the replacement of the amino group by the halogen atom in the corresponding nitro-amino derivatives of xylenes (Ahrens, *Annalen*, 1892, 271, 17; Bamberger and Reber, *Ber.*, 1913, 46, 199; Blanksma, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1913, I, 1108; Noeltling, Braun and Thesmar, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 2253). Only two nitro derivatives, 4-chloro-5-nitro-*o*-xylene, and 2-chloro-5-nitro-*p*-xylene, have been obtained by direct nitration by the action of concentrated nitric acid (Claus, Croneweg, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1894, ii, 43, 257; *Compt. rend.*, 1933, 196, 1896).

The nitro-derivatives of the halogenated xylenes have been obtained in good yields by nitrating the respective monohalogenated derivatives in presence of nitrosulphonic acid mixture, containing about 50% of fuming nitric acid. The following compounds have thus been prepared: (1) 4-chloro-6-nitro-*m*-xylene, (2) 2-chloro-5-nitro-*p*-xylene, (3) 4-bromo-6-nitro-*m*-xylene, (4) 2-bromo-5-nitro-*p*-xylene (5) 4-iodo-6-nitro-*m*-xylene and (6) 2-iodo-5-nitro-*p*-xylene. Of these the nitro-derivative of 2-iodo-*p*-xylene has been prepared for the first time and from analogy the new compound is probably 2-iodo-5-nitro-*p*-xylene.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Chloro-6-nitro-m-xylene.—To 4-chloro-*m*-xylene (7 c.c.) and acetic anhydride (5 c. c.) nitrosulphonic acid mixture (9 c. c.) was added slowly and the flask cooled under tap-water from time to time. When the whole of the nitrating mixture was added, the mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for about 4 hours. The product after washing with water and then with sodium bicarbonate solution was extracted with benzene. After recrystallisation from ether it melted at 42° and was identified to be 4-chloro-6-nitro-*m*-xylene, yield 6.8 g.

2-Chloro-5-nitro-p-xylene was obtained in a similar way from *2-chloro-p-xylene* (5 c. c.). The product crystallised from ether, m. p. 78°; yield 5.6 g. (Found: N, 7.47. $C_8H_8O_2NCl$ requires N, 7.55 per cent). From the sodium bicarbonate extracts small quantity of *3-chloro-p-toluic acid*, m. p. 200.2° were obtained, yield 0.4 g.

4-Bromo-6-nitro-m-xylene was obtained similarly from *4-bromo-m-xylene* (5 c. c.), m. p. 57°, yield 5.2 g.

2-Bromo-5-nitro-p-xylene, m. p. 70°, can be obtained in the same way from *2-bromo-p-xylene* (5 c. c.), yield 5.7 g.

4-Iodo-6-nitro-m-xylene can be obtained from *4-iodo-m-xylene* (5 c. c.). It melts at 86°, yield 4.8 g.

2-Iodo-5-nitro-p-xylene.—To *2-iodo-p-xylene* (3 c. c.) and acetic anhydride (3.5 c. c.), nitrosulphonic acid mixture (7 c. c.) was added drop by drop in about 15 minutes and then heated on a water-bath for about 2 hours. The product was subjected to the same treatment as mentioned above. It melts at 83°, yield 4.5 g. (Found: N, 4.98. $C_8H_8O_2NI$ requires N, 5.06 per cent).